

Synthesis of γ -(5-Arylhypdantoin-5)-Butyric Acids**

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It has been reported¹ that β -(5-arylhypdantoin-5)-propionic acids showed antitubercular activity. This prompted us to prepare the next higher homologue, viz. hypdantoin derivatives of γ -arylbutyric acids for pharmacological screening. Our earlier attempts² to prepare β -aryl- γ -(5-arylhypdantoin-5)-butyric acids from β -aryl- γ -arylbutyric acids by Bucherer-Berg reaction failed due to steric hindrance of bulky β -aromatic group in butyric acids. Hence, an attempt was made to prepare γ -(5-arylhypdantoin-5)-butyric acids from γ -arylbutyric acids, which were readily converted into hypdantoin derivatives by Bucherer reaction.

The γ -arylbutyric acids have been prepared by Friedel-Crafts reaction between substituted benzene derivatives(I) and glutaric anhydride (Fig. 1) by

Fig. 1

TABLE-1
 γ -(SUBSTITUTED AROYL)BUTYRIC ACIDS(II) AND
 γ -[5-(SUBSTITUTED ARYL)HYDANTOIN-5]-BUTYRIC ACIDS(III)

No.	R	R ₁	R ₂	II			III			Procedure	
				mp/bp °C	Yield %	Procedure	m.p. °C	Yield %	Found N %		Reqd. N %
1	H	H	H	132	60	A	177.5	55	10.54	10.68	C
2	CH ₃	H	H	—	—	—	133.0	—	10.83	10.15	—
3	H	H	4-CH ₃	148	40	A	185.0	60	10.04	10.14	C
4	CH ₃	H	4-CH ₃	—	—	—	178.0	—	9.42	9.65	—
5	H	H	4-OCH ₃	138	61	B	180.0	60	10.15	9.59	C
6	CH ₃	H	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	151.5	—	9.07	9.15	—
7	H	H	4-Cl	121	65	A	210.0	65	9.70	9.45	C
8	CH ₃	H	4-Cl	35	—	—	184.0	—	9.88	9.32	—
9	H	H	4-C ₂ H ₅	98	50	B	175.0	44	10.24	9.66	C
10	CH ₃	H	4-C ₂ H ₅	40	—	—	184.5	—	9.36	9.21	—
11	H	3-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	139	71	B	234.0	90	9.25	9.15	D
12	CH ₃	3-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	183.0	—	9.60	8.70	—
13	H	3-Cl	4-OCH ₃	156	80.3	B	215.0	70	9.27	8.58	D
14	CH ₃	3-Cl	4-OCH ₃	76	—	—	185.0	—	8.29	8.22	—
15	H	3-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	142	41	B	227.5	74	9.01	8.69	D
16	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	—	204.0	—	8.64	8.34	—
17	H	2-CH ₃	4-OCH ₃	121	70	B	—	—	—	—	—
18	H	2-Cl	5-OCH ₃	105	61	B	—	—	—	—	—
19	CH ₃	2-Cl	5-OCH ₃	190/1mm (bath)	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
20	H	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	114-6	48	B	Did not form hypdantoin derivative				—
21	CH ₃	2-Cl	4-OCH ₃	200/1mm (bath)	—	—					—
22	H	2-OCH ₃	4-OCH ₃	—	—	B	—	—	—	—	—
23	H	2-OCH ₃	5-OCH ₃	—	—	B	—	—	—	—	—

- Remarks: 1. All m.p./b.p. are uncorrected.
2. All the compounds have given satisfactory carbon, hydrogen and chlorine analyses wherever required.
3. Molecular weights of all the compounds were confirmed by mass spectrometry.

one of the methods (Table 1) given in the experimental part. Amongst them are five new γ -keto acids (II 7, 9, 13, 18, 20) which were characterised by preparing their esters (Table 1) and infra-red spectroscopy (aromatic CO : 1675-1660, carboxyl CO : 1710-1690 cm^{-1}). The γ -aroylbutyric acids were subjected to Bucherer-Berg reaction to get γ -(5-arylhydantoin-5)-butyric acids (Fig. 1) which were identified by infrared spectroscopy⁸ (2-CO : 1710-1690 cm^{-1} , 4-CO : 1790-1775 cm^{-1} , carboxyl CO : 1740-1730 cm^{-1} , NH doublet : 3400-3180 cm^{-1}) and by preparing their esters (Table 1). The compounds were tested for antitubercular activity and all of them were found to be completely inactive.

It is evident from Table 1 that γ -aroylbutyric acids (II 17, 18, 20, 22, 23) having ortho substituents in aryl ring failed to give hydantoin derivatives. Again the failure is attributed to steric hindrance of ortho group as noticed earlier². Prolonged reaction time in the conversion of γ -(disubstituted aroyl) butyric acids into hydantoin derivatives was also observed.

Experimental

γ -Aroylbutyric acid (II)

Procedure A

γ -(*p*-Chlorobenzoyl)-butyric acid (II.7) : AlCl_3 (16 g) was gradually added to a cooled (0-5°) solution of glutaric anhydride (5.7 g, 0.05 *M*) in dry chlorobenzene (100 ml) over 1/2 hr, while the flask was swirled for proper mixing. Then the mixture was heated on steam bath until the evolution of HCl gas ceased. It was then cooled under tap and decomposed by ice and conc. HCl. Excess of chlorobenzene was removed in steam and the residue was digested with 10% solution of NaHCO_3 (100 ml). The cold aqueous filtrate was washed with ether and pure acid was precipitated from acidified aqueous layer, recrystallised from boiling water to get white needles, m.p. 121°, yield 7.4 g (65%) Me ester : m.p. 35°.

Procedure B

γ -(*p*-Ethylbenzoyl)-butyric acid (II.9) : Ethyl benzene (10.6 g, 0.1 *M*), nitrobenzene (10 ml), tetrachloroethane (15 ml) was cooled (0-5°) in a three necked 250 ml round bottom flask, equipped with a stirrer, dropping funnel, calcium chloride guard tube and a gas outlet tube. Powdered AlCl_3 (27 g, 0.2 *M*) was added to it. A solution of glutaric anhydride (11.4 g, 0.1 *M*) in 25 ml of tetrachloroethane was gradually added through the dropping funnel over 3/4 hr. with vigorous stirring. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 24 hr and worked up as described in procedure A. White needles m.p. 98°, yield 5.5 g (50%), Me ester : m.p. 40°.

γ -(5-Arylhantoin-5)-butyric acid(III)

Procedure C

γ -(5-phenylhydantoin-5)-butyric acid(III. 1) :

γ -Benzoyl-butyric acid(II. 1)(3.84 g, 0.02 *M*), potassium cyanide (3.25 g, 0.025 *M*), ammonium carbonate (7.68 g, 0.08 *M*) and water (50 ml) were mixed in a 100 ml round bottom flask fitted with an air condenser. The flask was warmed at 60° for 10 hr and at 85° for further 3 hr. It was then cooled under tap, acidified with dil. HCl and kept overnight. The white ppt. washed with water, recrystallised from boiling water gave white needles, m.p. 177.5°, yield 2.88 g (55%), Me ester : m.p. 133°.

Procedure D

γ -[5-(3-Methyl-4-methoxyphenyl)-hydantoin-5]-butyric acid(III. 11) : γ -(3-methyl-4-methoxy-phenyl) butyric acid(II. 11), (4.24 g, 0.02 *M*), potassium cyanide (3.25 g, 0.025 *M*), ammonium carbonate (7.68 g, 0.08 *M*) and water (50 ml) were mixed in a 100 ml round bottom flask, fitted with an air condenser. The flask was warmed at 60° for 15 hr and at 85° for further 5 hr. The cooled reaction mixture was acidified with dl. HCl. The overnight white ppt. when washed with water, recrystallised from boiling water gave white needles, m.p. 234°, yield 4.28 g (70%), Me ester : m.p. 183°.

Biological Tests

The hydantoin derivatives were screened against mycobacterium tuberculosis Var hominis H_{37}Rv_1 in Youman's medium. None of the compounds were found active.

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Chemical Constituents of the Stem and Roots of *Xanthium strumarium* Linn

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XANTHIUM strumarium Linn (Compositae) is a medicinal plant and the roots are useful as bitter tonic, in strumous diseases and cancer¹. In our earlier reports^{2,3} we have investigated the leaves of this plant and the present paper is related to our findings on the stem and roots of *X. strumarium*.

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